

WORD COMBINATIONS DURING COVERT ARTICULATORY REPRODUCTION OF SPEECH SIGNALS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7475869>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 13th December 2022

Accepted: 21th December 2022

Online: 23th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Prediction, simultaneous interpreting, articulatory reproduction, probabilistic forecasting, semantic development, speech-motor analyzer.

ABSTRACT

This article analyses the importance of probabilistic predicting in simultaneous interpreting, and explains how perception and understanding of speech occur based on recognition of words and word combinations during covert articulatory reproduction of speech signals.

Introduction.

Based on the existence of the simultaneous implementation of perception and speaking in simultaneous translation, the question inevitably arises, by what mechanisms this simultaneity is ensured? It seems to us that this issue is not exhausted by the concept that explains the overlap in time of the processes of speaking of the speaker and the interpreter by the presence of a mechanism and probabilistic forecasting, thanks to which the interpreter "... based on the assessment of apriori probabilities of the implementation of this verbal situation puts forward counter hypotheses of semantic development or completion of the verbal intention of the speaker.

Main part.

It is difficult to advance any against the essence of the concept itself or any objections. The experimental material at our disposal also testifies about the fact

that before the start of translation, as a result of orientation in a situation of communication, the interpreter's mind develops ideas that anticipate the goal, topic and semantic content of statements of the speaker. In the course of translation, the interpreter develops and refines these ideas, constantly puts forward assumptions about the syntactic structures of statements and their lexical content and clarifies his hypotheses with the help of orientation in the speaker's speech.

Continuous probabilistic prediction of the speaker's speech at several levels at once facilitates the work of an interpreter, since presets it to solve continuously emerging translation tasks, allowing them to be identified by individual signs instead of their full perception and analysis. The interpreter's pre-setting for actions in upcoming situations, the probability of which is the maximum, is, in our opinion, the role of probabilistic forecasting in

simultaneous translation, as, however, in other types of human activity Feygenberg I. M.

But such arguments have no explanatory power when it is necessary to answer the question of how the translator manages to correctly and completely translate the speech of the speaker if 80-85% of the latter is deployed during the speaking of the translator. Predict the semantic content and lexico-grammatical organization of statements based on their fragment in 15-20% - such a task can be accomplished only by a scientist who knows the appropriate methodology to do it. It is also unclear in this case how with the help of what mechanisms the interpreter confirms (or rejects) his hypothesis when the critical points of the original message coincide with the speaking periods of the interpreter. Thus, the presence of a mechanism of probabilistic forecasting does not remove the task of identifying those mechanisms that allow the interpreter to perceive and understand the speech of the speaker during periods of pronunciation of the text in the target language.

In the conditions of normal speech activity, perception and understanding of speech occur based on recognition of words and word combinations during covert articulatory reproduction of speech signals. In simultaneous interpreting, during the periods of pronouncing the text in the target language, the participation of the speech-motor analyzer in recognizing speech signals in the source language is extremely limited. The limited possibilities of using the speech-motor code for translating the speaker's speech into their internal language encourages interpreters to look for other possibilities for

recognizing speech signals and short-term retention of extracted information in memory.

A survey of interpreters indicates that for the perception and understanding of the speaker's speech during their speaking, along with the motor speech code, a new subjective code is used, which is formed during training, as a rule, without awareness of this phenomenon by an interpreter. The basis of the functioning of this code is the recognition of words and phrases only based on their auditory images without counter-articulation reproduction to oneself, as well as keeping in mind received information in the form of visual and auditory sensations.

When translating speeches delivered on average and especially rapidly, an important role in the successful implementation of simultaneous translation plays the interpreter's ability to perceive the speech of the speaker during periods of speech in the target language. Perception of the speaker's speech during periods of pronunciation speech in the target language is ensured by the joint functioning of several mechanisms, the specific combination of which depends on the characteristics of the interpreter's personality. Among such mechanisms, we can mention the recognition of speech images by their acoustic ones characteristics with minimal participation of the speech-motor analyzer, pronunciation of the text on the language of translation with regular micro pauses within speech links to perceive individual fragments of words with an unoccupied articulatory apparatus.

Conclusion.

Adequate forecasting by the interpreter, possible development and outcome of the

utterance speaker allows him to recreate in his mind the content and form of the original statement based on the perception of the individual, most informative

fragments. Equally important is also the pre-adjustment to translation actions in situations, the likelihood of which is presented to the translator as maximum.

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